

ISic3638

I.Sicily inscription 3638

Language

Ancient Greek

Type

funerary

Material

marble

Object

tabula

Editor

Jonathan Prag

Principal Contributor

Jonathan Prag

Contributors

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Autopsy

No Autopsy

Last Change

2020-11-26 - Simona Stoyanova restructured bibliography

Place of origin (ancient)

Gaulus

Place of origin (modern)

Gozo

Provenance**Coordinates****Current Location**

Italy, Sicily, Valletta, Malta, National Archaeological Museum

Physical Description

Dimensions

Height cm

Width cm

Depth cm

Layout

Execution

Engraved

Letter Forms

Letter heights:

Line 1: mm

Interlineation

Interlineation line 1 to 2: mm

Text

Edition: PHI140931

1. ἐνθάδε κῆτε Δομέ-
2. στικός ὁ εὐμ[αθ]ῆς
3. Χριστιανὸς κ (αἰ) ἰητρός ²⁶ἰατρός²⁶.
4. ἔζησεν ἔτη ος',
5. ἀνεπάσατο ²⁶ἀνεπαύσατο²⁶ τῆ π,ρ(ὸ) ιη'
6. καλ [αν] δ (ὦν) □ Φεβρ (ουαρίων) .
- 7.

Apparatus

Translation

Commentary

Digital identifiers:

TM 285179

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Bibliography

- Kaibel, G. 1890. Inscriptiones Graecae Siciliae et Italiae, additis graecis Galliae Hispaniae, Britanniae, Germaniae inscriptionibus. *Inscriptiones Graecae consilio et auctoritate Academiae Litterarum Regiae Borussicae Editae. Volumen XIV.* Berlin. At 14.0604 (<https://clio.columbia.edu/catalog/6873760>)
- 1888-. L'année épigraphique: revue des publications épigraphiques relatives a l'antiquité romaine.. *L'année épigraphique : revue des publications épigraphiques relatives a l'antiquité romaine.* At 2008.0603
- Boeckh, A., Franz, J., Curtius, E., Kirchhoff, A., Roehl, H. 1828-1887. Corpus Inscriptionum Graecarum. Berlin. At 4.9451
- Wessel, C. 1989. Inscriptiones Graecae Christianae Veteres Occidentis. *Inscriptiones Christianae Italiae.* Bari. At 144
- Cassia, M. 2008. Christian Medicine and Late Antique Surgery: Illness and Healing in the Maltese Islands and Sicily in the 4th-5th century A.D.. In Bonanno, A., Militello, P.(eds.), *Interconnections in the Central Mediterranean: The Maltese Islands and Sicily in History.* Palermo. pp. 53-68. At ph

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